

Command-line arguments for programs

FastQC - <https://github.com/s-andrews/FastQC>

fastqc -threads <num_threads> -o <outfile_dir> <name_of_outfile>

Trimmomatic - <https://github.com/usadellab/Trimmomatic>

java jar trimmomatic-0.39.jar PE <read1_file> <read2_file> <paired1_outfile>
<unpaired1_outfile> <paired2_outfile> <unpaired2_outfile> ILLUMINACLIP:
adapters.fa:2:30:10 LEADING:3 TRAILING:3 SLIDINGWINDOW:4:15 MINLEN:36

SOAPdenovo-Trans - <https://github.com/aquaskyline/SOAPdenovo-Trans>

SOAPdenovo-Trans-31mer all -s <config input file> -o <outfile> -K 25

Gapcloser - <https://sourceforge.net/projects/soapdenovo2/files/GapCloser/src/r6/>

Gapcloser -b <SOAPdenovo-Trans_config_file> -a <.scafSeq file> -o <outfile> -l
<max_read_length> -t <num_threads>

CDHIT - <https://github.com/weizhongli/cdhit>

cd-hit-est -i <input_file> -o <outfile> -T 0

TransDecoder - <https://github.com/TransDecoder/TransDecoder>

TransDecoder.LongOrfs -t <path to transcript file>

Diamond BLAST - <https://github.com/bbuchfink/diamond>

diamond blastp -p <number of threads> -q longest_orfs.pep -d uniref90 -k 1 -e 0.00001 -o <.tsv
outfile> --very-sensitive

HMMER - <https://github.com/EddyRivasLab/hmmer>

hmmsearch -cpu <number of threads> --domtblout <outfile> <path to protein database>
longest_orfs.pep

TransDecoder

TransDecoder.Predict -t <path to transcript file> --retain_pfam_hits <path to domtblout file> --
retain_blastp_hits <path to BLASTP outfile>

Orthofinder - <https://github.com/davidemms/OrthoFinder>

orthofinder -M msa -oa -f <path to transcript files>

HMMER

for f in \$(ls *.fa); do echo "Processing file: \${f}"; hmmbuild \${f}.hmm \${f}; done

Orthofisher - <https://github.com/JLSteenwyk/orthofisher>

orthofisher -m <hmm_paths_file> -f <longorf_pep_paths_file> -b 0.95

MUSCLE - <https://www.drive5.com/muscle/>

muscle -align <input.fa> -output <output_file>

Trimal - <https://github.com/inab/trimal>

trimal -in <infile> -automated1 -out <outfile> -htmlout <html_outfile>

Prottest - <https://github.com/ddarriba/prottest3>

java jar protest-3.4.2.jar -i <path_to_fasta_file> -o <output_file> -all-distributions -F -AIC -BIC -S 2 -threads <num_threads>

MrBayes - <https://github.com/NBISweden/MrBayes>

MrBayes file has been uploaded to our Dryad repository.

IQtree - <http://www.iqtree.org>

iqtree -nt AUTO -s <input> -m <evolutionary_model> -bb 1000 -pre <outfile>

Phyutility - <https://github.com/blackrim/phyutility>

phyutility -concat -in <infiles> -out <concatenated_outfile>

IQtree

iqtree -nt AUTO -s <aln_file> -spp <partition_file> -bb 1000 -pre <outfile>

ASTRAL - <https://github.com/smirarab/ASTRAL>

java jar astral.5.7.1.jar -i <input_tree_file> -o <outfile> 2> <logfile>

Sortadate - <https://github.com/FePhyFoFum/SortaDate>

1. Root-to-tip variance → python src/get_var_length.py
<path_to_rooted_single_gene_trees> --flend.<file_extension_of_single_gene_trees> --
outf var --outg

<pyryez_1KPTI,porumb_Phytozome,graliv_1KPTI,gratur_1KPTI,gracat_1KPTI,ahnfla_1KPTI,glofur_1KPTI,mazjap_1KPTI,chocri_Ensembl,galsul_Ensembl,cyamer_Ensembl,cyayan_NCBI>

2. Bipartition support → python src/get_bp_genetrees.py
<path_to_rooted_phylogeny_tree_file> --flend <file_extension_of_single_gene_trees> --outf bp
3. Combine results of files “var” and “bp” generated in steps 1 and 2 → python src/combine_results.py var bp --outf comb
4. Sort and generate list of genes according to best scores of either root-to-tip variance, tree length, or bipartition → python src/get_good_genes.py examples/comb --max 3 --order 3,1,2 --outf gg

Phylobayes - <http://www.atgc-montpellier.fr/phylobayes/>

Phylobayes 4.1b was compiled with GSL library version 2.7.1. GSL was loaded into our cluster env prior to starting all Phylobayes runs.

```
pb -d <alignment_file> -T <ML_phylogeny_in_newick_tree_format> -cal  
<fossil_calibration_file> -r <outgroup_file> -bd -sb -<cir, wn, ln, or ugam> -lg -dgam 4 -rp 2000  
500 <outfile_name>
```

Phytools and MBASR - <https://github.com/liamrevell/phytools> and
<https://github.com/stevenheritage/MBASR/releases>

All Phytools scripts have been uploaded to the Dryad repository, and a template script for MBASR was also uploaded to Dryad.